

Microwave sinterability of pure and CuO doped ZnO macroporous ceramic foams with deposited zinc oxide nanoparticles produced by bioinspired replica technique

Cardoso, A. L. F.^{1 a}, Maestrelli, S. C.² Perdomo, C. P. F.¹ Kiminami, R. H. G. A.¹, Gunnewiek, R. F. K.¹

¹ Federal University of São Carlos, Post Graduate Program in Materials Science and Engineering, rod. Washington Luiz km 235, São Carlos - SP, Brazil. 13565-905

² Institute of Science and Technology, Federal University of Alfenas, Rod. José Aurélio Vilela 11999 (BR 267), km 533, Poços de Caldas - MG, Brazil, 37715-400

^a andre.lf.cardoso93@gmail.com

Abstract

Macroporous open-celled ceramic foams finds applications in numerous technological fields, like particle filters, insulating coatings, porous support for catalyst and photocatalyst processes, and even photoelectrochemical applications. In latter two, a macroporous open cell structure favors photoelectrochemical and photocatalyst reactions, due to its higher surface area. Many methods are used for producing these types of ceramics, specially the replica technique. In this simple method, the samples are obtained by impregnating a highly porous polymeric foam with a high solid loading ceramic slurry. After thermal treatment, the macroporous ceramic presents the structure of the polymeric foam used as template. Exceptionally complex and regular geometries can also be found in nature, which is the case of the *Luffa sp* sponge, that can replace the use of synthetic polymeric foams. In this work, microwave sinterability of porous ceramics obtained by impregnation of high solid loading ceramic slurries of nanostructured zinc oxide in natural *Luffa sp* fibrous sponges. Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), xanthan gum (XG) and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) were assessed as binder agents. Ceramic slurries were prepared by dispersing nanostructured zinc oxide in distilled water (70% wt. ratio) using ammonium polyacrylate (APA) as deflocculant, followed by mixing in a high shear mixer (IKA Ultra-Turrax T25) for 10 minutes. After homogenization, binders were added and mixed in mechanical mixer for 10 minutes. The sponges (with dimensions of 2x2x1 cm) were carefully immersed in the ceramic slurry, squeezed to remove excess and then left to dry 24h in air. The dried ceramic foams were microwave heated at 550 °C during 10 minutes with 100 °C/min heating rate, followed by microwave sintering at 1150 and 1200 °C during 15 minutes with a 100 °C/min heating rate. The microwave sintered samples were analyzed by optical and scanning electron microscopy, photocatalysis efficiency and density measurements. The advantages of microwave processing are evident. The microwave sintering temperature was reduced by at least 150 °C in comparison to the conventional.

Keywords: Microwave, Chemical applications, Processing, Characterisation.

Introduction

In the recent years, many methods of producing ceramic materials have been studied. Among these methods, for producing microporous and reticulated ceramic foams, the replica technique takes place as a promising way to produce these types of ceramics. This method is based on impregnation of ceramic slurry in a sponge (synthetic or natural) followed by heat treatment. It is a method employed in producing reticulated ceramic foams for many types of applications, including particle filters, catalysis/photocatalysis supports in gas-phase and liquid-phase reactions and insulating coatings. Moreover,

macroporous ceramic foams present a large surface area with a relatively low density, suitable for many other applications since it can be produced from different types of starting ceramic powders [1-3]. Some attention is needed for hazardous and carcinogenic wastes from industry that causes environment pollution, for example, rhodamine B (Rh-B), which is used as dye and is a common product present in effluents from textile, paper and leather industry, and before let-off in nature, this waste must be treated. It is well known that Zinc oxide function as a good material for photodegradation of Rh-B to a less toxic material [4]. In this work, we produced macroporous open celled zinc oxide ceramics prepared via replica technique using a natural sponge as template and employing microwave radiation for the heat treatment and sintering process of the ceramic foams.

Experimental procedure

The macroporous open celled zinc oxide ceramic foams presented in this work were produced by the replica technique using *Luffa sp* natural sponges as templates for impregnation. The preparation of the ceramic slurry used for impregnation consists in dispersing the 70% wt. ratio of ceramic oxide (pure ZnO, 1% and 5% molar CuO doped) in distilled water, deflocculated with ammonium polyacrylate (0,1% of solid weight). After manually mixing for about 1 minute, the suspension was mixed in a high shear mixer (ULTRA TURRAX T25) during 10 minutes. After homogenization, xanthan gum (XG) or carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) were added with polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) as binders, followed by mixing in a mechanical stirrer for about 10 minutes. The *Luffa sp* sponges were cut in 2x2x1 cm pieces and carefully immersed in the ceramic slurry, squeezing to remove excess and left to dry for 24h in air. After dried, test samples were heated at 550 °C during 30 minutes with 5 °C/min heating rate followed by sintering at 1300 °C during 60 minutes with 5°C/min heating rate. These sintering parameters were used for comparison with the microwave sintering parameters adopted in this work. In a semi-industrial microwave (COBER ELECTRONICS MS6K), the samples were heated at 550 °C during 10 minutes with 50 and 100 °C/min heating rates, followed by microwave sintering at 1150, 1200, 1250 and 1300 °C during 10 and 15 minutes with 100 °C/min heating rate (2,45 GHz and 2,8kW of maximum forward power). Figure 1 present the photographs of as-sintered ceramic foams, depicting its aspects. After sintering, a solution of 1M zinc acetate in water were prepared adding a small amount of PVA, under vigorous mixing at 40 °C. The as-sintered samples were immersed in this solution under continuous mixing for 15 minutes. Those samples were heat treated at 500 °C during 2 hours with 5 °C/min heating rate, forming zinc oxide nanoparticles deposited in the macroporous ceramic foams. The microwave sintered samples and zinc oxide nanoparticles deposited samples were analyzed by scanning electron microscopy (PHILIPS-XL30-FEG) and evaluated through Rh-B photocatalytic degradation under UV light. The photodegradation reactor was composed of four 15W UV light bulbs and a cooling system to avoid thermal degradation. Water was used as blank and solutions of 5mg.L⁻¹ of Rh-B in water were prepared for the tests. The photocatalytic potentials of the samples were assessed after overnight incubation of the Rh-B solution to ensure the diffusion of the particles of the dye on samples. The tests were taken in dark and after 15, 30, 45, 60, 90 and 120 minutes of UV light exposure, scanning the UV-Vis absorbance spectrum from 400 to 800 nm range in an Agilent Technologies Cary 60 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The relative density of the samples was measured following the ASTM C373-88 standard for whiteware fired products.

Fig. 1 – Microwave sintered samples: A) pure ZnO (with CMC); B) pure ZnO (with XG); C) ZnO + 1% CuO (with CMC); D) ZnO + 5% CuO (with CMC).

Results and discussion

The production of this macroporous open celled ceramics must be evaluated in regard to the quality of the final product. One of the desired characteristics of this open celled structure lies on the fact that the reticulated structure of the natural sponge must be covered with ceramic while maintaining the macropores opened, to ensure the maximum possible specific surface area. This was achieved in most samples, with carefully squeezing the ceramic slurry excess from the sponge template before letting it to dry. To ensure that to happen, a careful control of the ceramic slurry properties (solid content and additives) must be done, to prevent for example, cracks in the ceramic foam after dried. It was noticed in dried samples, that using XG combined with PVA as binders produced samples with fewer cracks in comparison with samples prepared using CMC and PVA. This occurs because CMC can induce shear localization, which results in high shear rate regions along the sample. This effect might lead the sample to behave like a solid under shear stress, further leading to formation of cracks. In contrast, this effect occurred to a lesser extent with the use of XG, associated with a lower shear-thinning index (stronger thinning behaviour) compared with CMC, leading to fewer cracks during the drying [3].

Fig. 2 depicts the SEM images of the ZnO and CuO-doped ceramics microwave sintered at 1150 °C for 10 minutes. It can be noticed that sinterability of the samples improved by adding CuO as dopant, increasing its relative density. This effect occurs because copper reduces the activation energy for grain growth of zinc oxide, promoting growth of grains and thus increasing the relative density [5]. The density depends both on grain growth and pore enclosure during sintering of the sample, and the latter also increased, noticed by analyzing the SEM micrographs, so it is intuitive that the density of CuO-doped samples would increase. It is also noticeable that as we increase the quantity of CuO in samples, a Cu-rich secondary phase segregates to grain boundary, depicted in the SEM-EDS elemental mapping of the 5% CuO-doped sample (Fig. 3). This segregation of a Cu-rich secondary phase was also observed in previous studies of Chiou and Chung [6] and Bellini, Morelli and Kiminami [7]. The increase of sintering temperature aided the

densification until 1250 °C, where after this temperature the relative density of samples decreased, as shown in Table 1. This indicates that the optimal microwave sintering temperature was reduced by at least 50 °C compared to conventional sintering (which is 1300 °C) [8].

Table 1 – Relative density of microwave sintered samples with 10 and 15 minutes of soaking time.

Relative Density (%)	1150 °C (10 min)	1200 °C (10 min)	1250 °C (10 min)	1250 °C (15 min)	1300 °C (10 min)	1300 °C (15 min)
ZnO (XG)	47,45%	91,30%	75,57%	76,30%	76,91%	71,79%
ZnO (CMC)	59,98%	69,22%	77,06%	78,95%	77,25%	76,91%
ZnO + 1% CuO	52,95%	51,65%	78,26%	75,94%	73,82%	73,11%
ZnO + 5% CuO	78,74%	73,77%	79,23%	80,10%	78,77%	71,27%

Fig. 2 – Samples microwave sintered at 1150 °C for 10 min: A) pure ZnO (with XG), B) ZnO + 1% CuO and C) ZnO + 5% CuO.

Fig. 3 – SEM-EDS elemental mapping of 5% CuO-doped sample microwave sintered at 1150 °C for 15 min.

The microwave sintered samples did not show significant efficiency of photodegrading the Rh-B (less than 5% after 120 minutes of UV light exposure), so it was tested whether if a deposition of zinc oxide nanoparticles covering the open-celled macroporous structures would affect positively this efficiency. Fig. 4 depicts the zinc oxide nanoparticles deposited on microwave sintered samples. The efficiency of those samples with nanoparticles deposited increased considerably, up to almost 30% of Rh-B degrading after 120 minutes of UV light exposure. The efficiency on the degradation of dyes is directly correlated with the generation of free radicals and the non-recombination of electron-hole pairs, besides the exposure of the sample surface to UV light, since the photocatalysis occurs in the exposed surface of the material. In terms of processing, the material characteristics must be highly porous, favoring the photocatalytic efficiency, with high structural integrity, obtained through sintering. The sintering step is critical since, although being fundamentally necessary to increase the mechanical strength of the final product, could compromise the photocatalytic properties due to partial closing of pores and promoting grain growth. This statement presented shows that some modifications on the sintering steps or composition formulation must be done to correct and enhance the photocatalytic activity and efficiency of this material, but also open up possibilities for different applications where a high relative surface area is needed.

Fig. 4 – SEM images of zinc oxide nanoparticles deposited in samples microwave sintered at 1150 °C during 10 min: A) pure ZnO and B) 5% CuO-doped.

Conclusions

The replica technique was successfully employed utilizing *Luffa sp* natural sponges as templates for ceramic slurry impregnation, producing open celled reticulated macroporous pure and CuO-doped zinc oxide ceramic foams. The samples were successfully microwave sintered, with densities ranging roughly from 50 to 80%, depending on sintering parameters adopted. Mildly porous microstructures with grains of about 0,5 to 1 μm were obtained. This was achieved with less than 1 hour of microwave heat treatment, compared to approximately 6 hours of conventional sintering time, besides reducing the optimal soaking temperature in 50 °C.

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